

A new and innovative mobile signage framework towards smart city branding and entrepreneurship

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Abstract:

Towards the accomplishment of smart city branding and entrepreneurship the concept of mobile signage can be integrated utilizing innovative concepts and trends if ICT aiming to develop innovative customer approach techniques. The proposed contribution aims to deliver a new framework in the area of smart city branding and entrepreneurship with the establishment of innovative infopoints delivering location based services to people through their smartphone devices.

1. Introduction

The concepts of smart city (Bowerman, et al, 2000) and smart city branding for tourists (Buhalis et al, 2013) are rather new and constitute two buzzwords of modern time. The purpose of the specific contribution is to present an innovative framework that establishes the basis to achieve the goals and aims of the vision of smart city branding.

The proposed framework uses ICT innovative solutions aiming to build an ICT infrastructure in places of interest giving the opportunity to residents and visitors to access information related to their interests through their mobile device.

The Smart City Branding Solution is based on state of the art ICT solutions aiming to develop a smart city concept for residents and visitors. The overall idea is to design and develop a system that can be used by clients (residents and visitors of a city) through their mobile device accessing information related to local entrepreneurship. The main objective is to define a framework for cooperation and development using ICT aiming to build an innovative solution for mobile signage applications and to connect local enterprises with their potential clients.

The mobile industry continues to scale rapidly, with a total of 3.6 billion unique mobile subscribers at the end of 2014. Half of the world's population now has a mobile subscription—up from just one in five 10 years ago. An additional one billion subscribers are predicted by 2020, taking the global penetration rate to approximately 60%. There were 7.1 billion global SIM connections at the end of 2014, and a further 243 million machine-to-machine (M2M) connections (GSMA, 2015).

Taking into account the penetration rate per capita of smartphones in Europe that will reach 64.7 percent until 2017 (Statista, 2016), it is quite obvious that the most important device for all people is their smartphone. People use their smartphone to connect themselves with the rest of the world and it's a device that the market should take into account during the design phase of new services.

Based on this, a new trend has appeared in the field of marketing with new means and tools offered to SMEs facilitating their need to approach potential customers and to deliver their message to people. The specific trend utilizes smartphones as the main device mechanism to deliver the message to the potential customer.

The specific contribution presents a framework solution of a wireless network infrastructure of info-kiosks providing mobile signage applications aiming to achieve the smart city branding vision.

2. Architecture of Smart City Framework Solution

The proposed solution is based on open architecture characteristics aiming to provide scalability features to it. The main architectural concept is being presented on the following diagram:

Figure 3: Architecture of Network

The proposed architecture develops a network of several points of interest with one common characteristic, big concentration of people. Based on this the overall idea is that each Info-Point will contain information regarding the specific point of interest in correlation with entrepreneurial information located in the specific and neighboring places.

It is critical to develop content for each point of interest that will be provided to the end user through its smartphone mobile device. Each user will access to information not only for the point of interest (museum, station, etc.) but also the user will have the possibility to familiarize with local enterprises around the POI.

3. Added Value to Entrepreneurship

The proposed network architecture is a breakthrough in the field of city branding. The reason is that up to now there are no networks that are designed to provide information regarding a point of interest (for any kind of user) correlated with location based information of the entrepreneurship of the specific area. Similar initiatives (Yoon, C.W. et al), (Sato, H., et al.) describe the technological solutions for a specific place – a single location. The specific approach integrates a network of infopoints providing information of the node installed in the specific place. However, moving to a different place will not affect the operation of the system, the content will be differentiated based on the location of the user.

The technological breakthrough is that the content will be given to the end user not over the internet, but it will be delivered to the end user by the local infopoint through a local infrastructure.

So, the end user will use the smartphone that will give the possibility to access information stored on the InfoPoint. The application that will deliver the information must be built with open standards aiming to integrate and present to the user two different things:

1. The information about the Point of Interest
2. The information that local enterprises submit to the end user.

The specific methodology of an integrated environment that will present this two different types of information is more than interesting, since that in this way the end users will use their most personal device (the smartphone) to access information regarding an issue that interests them and concurrently have the opportunity to browse the enterprises located in the area and to access information stored by these enterprises in real time.

It is important to note that the specific concept will operate in a network providing location based services giving the opportunity to visitors of POI to be guided to POIs nearby by the proposed system and eventually if the infopoints are enough to cover all the main POIs of a specific city and the deliver a real time guide for POIs and Entrepreneurship directly to potential customers utilising their smart phones.

4. Conclusion

The proposed contribution introduces a new concept in the field of smart city branding and promotion of enterprises. It proposes a network of infopoints providing location based information for Points of Interest correlated with local based enterprises.

Towards this the network through a scalable method provides the possibility to develop a real time guided tour promoting interesting places for visitors and residents giving the opportunity to enterprises to approach potential customers through the specific network of Info Points.

However, there is a lot of work to be done in the near future since that the proposed solution must be implemented in pilot scale in the near future.

Last but not least a future exploitation of the proposed solution is to take advantage of other trends of modern ICT Technologies such as Internet of Things, Ambient Intelligence and Ubiquitous Computing to design and develop smart environments for people aiming to minimize the need of a device for interacting with the end user.

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